

Analysis of User Community Satisfaction Kampung Rambutan Terminal

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ABSTRACT: The terminal is a manifestation of a road transportation node that serves the community as a transportation location, such as intra- and intermodal locations for passengers and loading and unloading of goods, as well as regulating the smooth flow of arrivals and departures of public vehicles. The purpose of this study is to determine the level of satisfaction and the level of service performance using objective measures to highlight changes that should be made to the Kampung Rambutan terminal service. The method used is to calculate based on the results of a questionnaire based on the standardization of PM No. 40 of 2015 and then process the results using the Customer Satisfaction Index (CSI) method to determine the public's perspective on services at the Kampung Rambutan terminal and Importance Performance Analysis (IPA) to map attributes that require priority improvement at the Kampung Rambutan terminal. The results of the analysis through CSI obtained a satisfaction index of 54.40%, meaning that service users are quite satisfied with the services provided. Meanwhile, IPA obtained 10 service attributes that require priority improvement. There are several important aspects that should be considered, such as environmental cleanliness, facilities for users with disabilities.

KEYWORDS: Kampung Rambutan Terminal, Customer Satisfaction Index (CSI), Importance Performance Analysis (IPA), Customer Satisfaction

I. INTRODUCTION

Transportation can be defined as the effort to move, deliver, transport, transfer, or relocate a product to a different location where it will be more beneficial or have a different useful purpose [1]. The high mobility flow in the city of Jakarta requires supporting factors such as good facilities and infrastructure so that transportation effectiveness continues to function. [2]. The government has offered transportation facilities that are expected to be used as much as possible by Jakarta residents to realize an effective and efficient transportation system [3, 4].

One of the facilities in the governance of public services is the highway as a primary network and passenger terminals as a node point where both are interconnected in the road transportation network system [5]. Of the various types of transportation, one of the most popular modes of consumer transportation also has problems, which is traffic congestion [6]. Information from the Central Bureau of Statistics shows that in 2016, there were 18,006,404 vehicles in Jakarta. and in the last 5 years experienced growth reaching 5.35 percent per year, resulting in problems such as congestion because the existing infrastructure cannot accommodate existing vehicles [7].

The terminal is a manifestation of a primary node of road transportation that functions as a place for public services such as the location of intra-and intermodal passengers and

loading and unloading of goods, as well as regulating the fluent traffic of arrivals and departures of public vehicles. [8]. The development of society is dynamic so the transportation and traffic systems should respond to these dynamics, including the terminal as supporting infrastructure. [9]. Facilities located at the terminal include supporting facilities and main facilities. The main terminal facilities are facilities that are mandatory and must be available in a terminal to provide services to the community, including the arrival and departure lanes for public transportation, terminal management office buildings, public vehicle waiting lanes, track lanes, and passenger waiting areas. While supporting facilities are complementary to the operation of the terminal. The complementary facilities at a terminal include prayer rooms, public telephones, toilets, canteens, medical rooms, information and complaint rooms, and parks. [10, 11].

Kampung Rambutan Terminal was operational on October 1, 1992, with an area of around 141,000 m². However, Kampung Rambutan Terminal has been operating without significant progress, giving rise to a number of problems. There are several variables, such as unclean terminals and inefficient vehicle circulation, such as the existence of bay terminals, as well as the irregularity of public transportation vehicles in carrying out their activities [12, 13]. Reported from the media that there was a friction at the terminal caused by a conflict over passengers between ticket sellers of bus

companies, and this conflict led to a fight and caused injuries to the conflicting parties (detik.com, 2020). This kind of phenomenon certainly makes it unsafe and uncomfortable for people who use the terminal.

II. RESEARCH METHOD

In general, every research project is carried out with a "research method" so that all processes to be completed can be fulfilled as planned and the research can be concluded at the point of decision-making [14]. Direct observation, interviews, and survey applications are used as primary data collection methods, and operators at Kampung Rambutan Terminal obtain secondary data. The research location can be seen in Figure 3.1 below: [15].

Figure 3. 1: Research location

Data processing and analysis using questionnaires and direct observations obtained in the field. This study is performed to obtain the results of the analysis in accordance with Department of Transportation Standards [16]. The data analysis approach of this research is qualitative and quantitative analysis methods [17, 18]. Customer Service Index (CSI) and Importance Performance Analysis (IPA) are used to measure how well Kampung Rambutan Terminal performs and provides satisfactory services related to the level of public satisfaction. The variable used is variable x, which is the level of performance and service. [19–21].

A. Questionnaire Design

The questionnaire is prepared based on indicators and attributes related to the Kampung Rambutan terminal service, the determination of variables refers to the terminal service standards based on PM No.40 of 2015. The parts in the questionnaire design, such as the background of Kampung Rambutan terminal service users, the level of service at the Kampung Rambutan terminal, and respondents' expectations of services at the Kampung Rambutan terminal.

B. Questionnaire Evaluation

The questionnaire that has been prepared will be tested on at least 30 service users as a sample, after the test, a validity test will be carried out using the bivariate formula as follows:

$$r = \frac{n(\Sigma \times Y) - (\Sigma Y)^2}{\sqrt{(n(\Sigma X^2) - (\Sigma X)^2) \times (n(\Sigma Y^2) - (\Sigma Y)^2)}} \tag{2.1}$$

Wherw:

- r = Correlation of item score with total score
- Xi = Item Scores
- Yi = Score Total number of items
- n = Number of Samples

in the validity test if r count > r table, then the variable being tested is declared valid. In the questionnaire test, the reliability test was also carried out using the Cronbach Alpha formula as follows:

$$\alpha = \frac{K}{K-1} \left(1 - \frac{\Sigma \alpha^2}{\alpha^2} \right) \tag{2.2}$$

Where:

- A = Coefficient of Reliability
- k = Total number of questions
- j² = Variant score of question i

using formula:

$$\delta^2 = \frac{\Sigma X^2 \Sigma (x)^2}{n} \tag{2.3}$$

Wherw:

- j² = Variant score of question i
- Xi = Score of Question-i
- N = Number of Respondents

Therefore, in the reliability test, if the count > table is positive, the research instrument tested is declared reliable. In calculating the questionnaire test, the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) tool can be used to determine the correlation between the level of satisfaction with each factor and the characteristics of the respondent.

C. Sample Determination

According to Guilford, the more samples, the results obtained will be more accuratet [22]. The sampling collection measurement used Slovin's method [23, 24]:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^2} \tag{2.4}$$

Wherw:

- n = Sample Size
- N = Population Size (Number of passengers per year)
- e = The margin of error is due to sampling (10%).

Number of respondents based on the number of passengers at Kampung Rambutan Terminal in 2022.

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Referring to the Slovin formula, an error margin of 10% will be used with passenger data per year, totaling 635,863 passengers, where the average passenger per day is 1,742 people. By using the Slovin formula, the number of samples in this study is as follows:

$$n = \frac{1.742}{1 + (1.742 \times (0.1)^2)} = 94 \text{ sample} \approx 100 \text{ sample}$$

In the collection of this questionnaire, the characteristics of the Kampung Rambutan Terminal passenger profile respondents were obtained in the form of gender, age, education, occupation, monthly income, travel frequency, travel destination, and transportation used.

A. Questionnaire Analysis

The data collected is from users of Kampung Rambutan Terminal as respondents obtained through the distribution of questionnaires. This questionnaire was given to 100 users who became respondents. The following is the data of the respondents in terms of gender, age, latest education, profession or occupation, and income level. In Figure 3.1, based on the results of filling out the questionnaire, it is known that the percentage of male respondents is 44 people, or less than the percentage of female respondents totaling 56 people.

Figure 3. 2: Characteristics Based on Gender

Figure 3.2 shows that from the results of filling out the questionnaire, it is known that the highest percentage of respondents are respondents aged 26-35 years, with a total of 36 people. Then, followed by respondents aged 36-45 years with 26 people, while the respondents with the least number were respondents aged > 45 years, totaling 8 people.

Figure 3. 3: Passengers by Age

Figure 3.3 shows that the largest percentage of respondents are respondents who work as private employees as many as 29 people, self-employed 21 people, government employees 19 people, and 15 students. While there were 16 respondents who answered other.

Figure 3. 4: Passengers Based on Occupation

Based on the results of filling out the questionnaire in Figure 3.4, it was found that the largest percentage of respondents had an average frequency of travel that was uncertain or other, with a total of 29 people. The second highest respondent's travel frequency was one week, with a total of 23 respondents. The number of respondents with a frequency of travel every day is 21 people, while the frequency of respondents traveling once a year is 13 people.

Figure 3. 5: Passengers Based on Trip Frequency

Figure 3.5 shows respondents with the purpose of traveling out of town, with a total of 34 respondents: for business, 26 people; for school or work, 21 people; and for recreation, 17 people.

Figure 3. 6: Passengers Based on Trip Purpose

Figure 5.6 shows that the largest percentage of respondents are respondents with public transportation modes (69 people),

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motorbikes (19 people), taxis (7 people), private cars (5 people).

Figure 3. 7: Passengers by Mode of Transportation

B. Analisa Customer Satisfaction Index (CSI)

CSI analysis is used as one method to determine the level of service user satisfaction by comparing the performance of evaluation variables (X) with passenger expectation variables (Y) on service quality. The results of the calculation of service performance and the level of passenger expectations are

calculated by finding the performance score, or Mean Satisfaction Score (Equation 2.1), that is, the amount of data from the tabulation of the performance assessment questionnaire for each attribute is divided by the number of respondents. As an example of this calculation, the results of the answers to variable 1 are taken:

Respondents answered, "very satisfied" (SP)= 2
 Respondents answered "Satisfied" (P) = 15
 Respondents answered, "Fairly Satisfied". (CP) = 48
 Respondents answered, " Moderately Satisfied" (KP) = 12
 Respondents answered, "Not Satisfied" (TP) = 23
 Total respondents (TR)= 100

The Mean Satisfaction Score value is obtained as follows:

$$MSS = (SP \times 5) + (P \times 4) + (CP \times 3) + (KP \times 2) + (TP \times 1) : TR$$

$$MSS = (2 \times 5) + (15 \times 4) + (48 \times 3) + (12 \times 2) + (23 \times 1) : 100$$

$$= 261 : 100$$

$$= 2,61$$

Comprehensive results for the calculation of MSS can be seen through table 3.1 below.

Table 3.1. Correlation ratio of service performance questionnaire according to passengers

Attribute	Score					Performance Score	MSS
	Very satisfied	Satisfied	Fairly satisfied	Moderately Satisfied	Not satisfied		
	5	4	3	2	1		
1	2	15	48	12	23	261	2,61
2	0	15	41	19	25	246	2,46
3	5	12	38	23	22	255	2,55
4	1	11	33	32	23	235	2,35
5	1	12	33	34	20	240	2,4
6	1	11	31	29	28	228	2,28
7	5	14	28	24	29	242	2,42
8	8	16	28	31	17	267	2,67
9	13	22	35	19	11	307	3,07
10	2	26	54	15	3	309	3,09
11	6	25	13	44	12	269	2,69
12	5	16	15	37	27	235	2,35
13	9	17	29	25	20	270	2,7
14	11	8	32	36	13	268	2,68
15	8	14	36	18	24	264	2,64
16	3	21	52	17	7	296	2,96
17	4	23	38	19	16	280	2,8
18	5	15	37	33	10	272	2,72
19	1	20	43	28	8	278	2,78
20	1	16	53	23	7	281	2,81
21	24	19	26	22	9	327	3,27
22	8	30	38	15	9	313	3,13
23	4	11	37	28	20	251	2,51
24	1	1	17	40	41	181	1,81

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25	1	19	44	30	6	279	2,79
26	9	31	29	24	7	311	3,11
27	9	27	41	20	3	319	3,19
28	6	30	43	19	2	319	3,19
29	11	25	32	20	12	303	3,03
30	0	17	43	23	17	260	2,6
Total						8166	81,66

After obtaining the results for the calculation of MSS, it is continued with the calculation of the mean importance Score (Equation 2.1), the tabulated data of the performance assessment questionnaire for each attribute is divided by the number of respondents. As an example of a calculation, the results of the answers to variable 1 are taken:

Respondents answered, "very satisfied" (SP)= 66
 Respondents answered "Satisfied" (P) = 29
 Respondents answered, "Fairly Satisfied". (CP) = 5
 Respondents answered, " Moderately Satisfied" (KP) = 0
 Respondents answered, "Not Satisfied" (TP) = 0
 Total respondents (TR)= 100

The Mean Importance Score (MIS) value is obtained as follows:

$$MIS = (SP \times 5) + (P \times 4) + (CP \times 3) + (KP \times 2) + (TP \times 1) : TR$$

$$MIS = (66 \times 5) + (29 \times 4) + (5 \times 3) + (0 \times 2) + (0 \times 1) : 100$$

$$= 461 : 100$$

$$= 4,61$$

Overall results for the calculation of MSI can be see through table 3.2. below:

Table 3.2. Correlation ratio of passenger expectation questionnaire

Attribute	Score					Performance Score	MSI
	Very satisfied	Satisfied	Fairly satisfied	Moderately Satisfied	Not satisfied		
	5	4	3	2	1		
1	66	29	5	0	0	461	4,61
2	65	28	7	0	0	458	4,58
3	63	20	17	0	0	446	4,46
4	60	26	13	1	0	445	4,45
5	73	20	7	0	0	466	4,66
6	60	31	9	0	0	451	4,51
7	66	26	8	0	0	458	4,58
8	72	22	6	0	0	466	4,66
9	38	16	46	0	0	392	3,92
10	62	25	13	0	0	449	4,49
11	69	27	4	0	0	465	4,65
12	57	29	14	0	0	443	4,43
13	66	26	8	0	0	458	4,58
14	61	20	19	0	0	442	4,42
15	69	19	11	1	0	456	4,56
16	71	19	10	0	0	461	4,61
17	55	28	17	0	0	438	4,38
18	59	34	7	0	0	452	4,52
19	49	39	12	0	0	437	4,37
20	59	29	11	1	0	446	4,46
21	64	32	4	0	0	460	4,6
22	51	33	16	0	0	435	4,35
23	61	28	11	0	0	450	4,5

24	62	20	18	0	0	444	4,44
25	51	42	7	0	0	444	4,44
26	64	29	7	0	0	457	4,57
27	64	20	16	0	0	448	4,48
28	63	29	8	0	0	455	4,55
29	52	29	19	0	0	433	4,33
30	60	34	6	0	0	454	4,54
Total						13455	134,55

WMT = Total sum of WS for each attribute

$$= 272,02$$

CSI = WMT : The largest scale in the scoring

$$CSI = 272,02 : 5$$

$$= 54,40$$

Through the results of survey calculations on 100 respondents, the customer satisfaction index value for Kampung Rambutan Terminal services is obtained with a result of 54.40%, which is based on the provision that if the value is <60%, it is stated that the passenger is quite satisfied with the service provided. Performance and Interest Compatibility Value are table 3.3 below:

Table 3.3. Calculation Result of Compatibility Level

Attribute	Performance Score	Expected Score	Compatibility Level (%)
	Xi	Yi	
29	303	433	69,98
30	260	454	57,27
TKI Total			60,69

The data is used to determine the perception of terminal service users on the quality of services that have been provided by the Kampung Rambutan terminal management. Referring to table 3.3, it is found that if the results of the level of conformity are high, the higher the level of importance of these services for service users. [25]. It can also be concluded that the Kampung Rambutan terminal requires improvement because the average value of the level of conformity is only 60.69%, referring to the provision that if the value of the level of conformity is 60-69%, the respondent is declared quite satisfied with the services that have been provided.

C. Importance Performance Analysis (IPA)

The calculation of the correlation ratio can be taken through the Mean Satisfaction Score (MSS) and Mean Importance Score (MIS) data that was obtained during the previous Customer Satisfaction Index (CIS) calculation.

Table 3.4. Hasil Perhitungan Rasio Korelasi X dan Y

No.	Correlation Ratio Y (MIS)	Correlation Ratio X (MSS)
1	4,61	2,61
2	4,58	2,46
3	4,46	2,55
4	4,45	2,35
5	4,66	2,4
6	4,51	2,28
7	4,58	2,42
8	4,66	2,67
9	3,92	3,07
10	4,49	3,09
11	4,65	2,69
12	4,43	2,35
13	4,43	2,7
14	4,42	2,68
15	4,56	2,64
16	4,61	2,96
17	4,38	2,8
18	4,52	2,72
19	4,37	2,78
20	4,46	2,81
21	4,6	3,27
22	4,35	3,13
23	4,5	2,51
24	4,44	1,81
25	4,44	2,79
26	4,57	3,11
27	4,48	3,19
28	4,55	3,19
29	4,33	3,03
30	4,54	2,6
Total	134,55	81,66
Average	4,49	2,72

Based on Table 3.4 above, a Cartesian diagram of the average assessment of the level of expectations and the performance level of each dimension is obtained as follows:

Figure 3. 8: Diagram kartesius Importance Performance Analysis

From the results of the analysis obtained, the assessment attributes are divided into four classifications. In each quadrant or classification, the importance values of each attribute for service users are known, and this quadrant can help terminal management prioritize improvements to attributes whose importance values are very high and affect the satisfaction of service users. In Figure 3.8 above, each attribute of the Cartesian diagram can be explained as follows:

1. This quadrant shows the attributes of terminal services that are considered to have a very high level of importance and greatly affect passenger satisfaction, but the attributes in this quadrant have unsatisfactory service and need to be prioritized for improvement management, such as the waiting room, information board, and disability user facilities.
2. This quadrant shows the attributes of terminal services that are considered to have a high level of importance and have services that are also considered satisfactory. In this case, the management has provided good service, so that service users are also satisfied with the services provided, such as security and safety facilities and terminal locations that are easy to access.
3. This quadrant shows the attributes of terminal services that are considered to have a low level of importance and have services that are also considered sufficient by service users. In this case, the management does not need to make excessive investments in the attributes that are in this quadrant, such as service information, places of worship, and food courts.
4. This quadrant shows the attributes of terminal services that are considered to have a low level of importance but have satisfactory service performance. In this case, the management is considered excessive in the services provided, so these attributes do not need to be a priority for improvement, such as ticket sales counters, health facilities, and room lighting.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The results of calculations using the Customer Satisfaction Index (CSI) method using data on the perceptions of the public who use Kampung Rambutan terminal services obtained a satisfaction index of 54.40%. It is concluded that respondents are quite satisfied with the performance of the Kampung Rambutan Terminal service attributes. Based on the results of the evaluation of service assessment at the Kampung Rambutan terminal by respondents using the Importance Performance Analysis method, it is concluded that there are several attributes that need to be prioritized for improvement because they have high values of suitability and importance, but the results of their performance are poor, such as waiting rooms, information boards, and disability user facilities.

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